

Speed of Massless Object is equal to the Speed of Light

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Abstract: This paper discusses an object in motion relating to the speed of light.

Keywords: motion, photon, gluon

1. Introduction

Object is a thing that can be seen, held, or touched, usually not a living thing. For example, air and light are objects: air has mass but light has no mass. In particle physics, a massless particle is an elementary particle whose invariant mass is zero. There are two known massless particles: photon and gluon. The speed of light in vacuum is known to be almost exactly 3×10^8 metres per second. Gluons are massless, travel at the speed of light, and possess a property called color.

2. Speed of Objects

Theoretically it is proved that the maximum speed of an object with mass in the universe is less than the speed of light [1, 2] because light has zero mass. Thus, an object with no mass can only move at the speed of light. Essentially, the universe has set the speed of light as the speed limit for all objects. This means that, in the universe, the speed of any object other than light can not be more than the speed of light.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the speed of an object with or without mass has been compared to the speed of light.

References

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